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Ayurvedic Health Tourism in Kerala: A Case Study on Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal

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Abstract

Tourism has expanded largely from a relatively small activity in the early 19th century to one of the largest industries in the world today. It is one of the world's fastest growing industries and it can play role in accelerating the economic development of the country. Health care, like any other basic needs, is a prime component of humanity. Health Tourism or Medical Tourism is one of the significant components of the Tourism Industry. Health tourism has become a major industry in the recent past. This branch of tourism is the most common type of cost-effectiveness and a chance to take benefits of the tourist attractions of health tourism centers or locations during the recovery time. In India, Kerala is emerging as a prime hub of health tourism for its traditional way of medical practices and is creating a worldwide trademark as 'The Medical Hub of Asia'. In health tourism, Ayurvedic tourism is the most popular and very much rooted in the tradition and culture of Kerala. Thus the acceptance and recognition of Ayurveda paved the way for the development and widened

up the opportunities and scope of this sector. The state is blessed with rich and varied resources and capable of providing different health care packages to tourists from different parts of the world. This study is mainly focusing on the role of Ayurveda in tourism of Kerala and the trend analysis of the tourism sector of the state. Data were collected from various secondary sources. Annual growth rates and percentage method were mainly used for the further analysis.

Keywords: Health tourism, Ayurvedic tourism, Tourism sector, Kerala and Ayurveda

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Introduction

Tourism has expanded largely from a relatively small activity in the early 19th century to one of the largest industries in the world today. According to a well-known ancient saying, “Man’s heart seeks rest, while his mind longs for knowledge”. One could argue that the desire to get away from the routine and explore a new world is what fuels the thriving and ever expanding tourism sector. There are different forms of tourism. One of the important kinds of tourism prevails is the health tourism. Health tourism comprises two terms healthcare and tourism which is the most preferred form of tourism and is the mixture of health care, leisure, and relaxation. Health tourism is a niche tourism developed by competing countries that promote tourism to attract people traveling with the prime purpose of getting healthcare. The trend of health tourism is growing as more and more Europeans, Americans and even individuals from underdeveloped nations travel for the purpose of timely medical care at reasonable costs.

Ayurveda has a significant impact on health tourism of Kerala. The Sanskrit term for Ayurveda is the science of life. It is composed of the Sanskrit terms “Veda”, which means knowledge and “Ayu” which means life. It is an age old, proven method of healing based on medication made from the many herbal plants that grow abundantly in India. This conventional approach has become more widely accepted in recent years, particularly for its alternative approaches to preventive, therapeutic and rejuvenating processes that enhance life. These days a lot of ayurvedic centers are growing since they are among the main destinations for tourists in

the southern area. The geographical, physiological features and a strong base of rich and powerful resources of Kerala attract tourists from all around the world. The long tradition of Ayurveda turns Kerala into a global destination of medical tourism. Various ayurvedic treatments are offered to the tourists here. The recognition and acceptance of Ayurveda in both national and international level paved a way for the promotion and development of this particular sector in the state.

Review of Literature

Leena Abraham (2013) made a study “From Vaidhyam to Kerala Ayurveda”. The study mainly discussed the various factors which contribute in institutionalizing Vaidhyam into Kerala ayurveda since 20th century. The major factor highlighted by them was the socio-political struggles by the subordinate castes and classes. They mainly referred to one of the renowned Ayurvedic institutions of Kerala, Kottakkal Arya Vaidya Sala, situated in Kottakkal in northern Kerala for the study. The study mainly discussed the socio-cultural transformation of a regional medicine and institutionalizing of ayurveda, and also its recent developments. Further the study moves to the Kerala’s tourism, the promotion strategies and the role of ayurveda in the tourism. As per the findings of the study, the increase in production and distribution and exports of ayurvedic drugs resulted in the more expansion of this sector.

Padmasani and Remya (2015) in the research, “Kerala: Health tourism hub for Ayurveda” tried to identify the strength of Kerala in the ayurvedic tourism with the help of service providers for elevating the ayurvedic tourism in Kerala. Research also provides detailed information on the domestic tourists visit in Kerala for Ayurvedic treatments. The primary data for the research was collected from 150 domestic tourists using questionnaire method and the secondary data was from various official reports. They employed the descriptive statistics, factor analysis and one-way ANOVA in order to analyse the objectives. The analysis of the research indicated that the Kerala can develop its image as ayurvedic health tourism destination. The service providers are advised to have a proper plan and well execution of the same, since there is a wider scope exists in this field.

K S Beena and D Venkatrama Raju (2018) in their study titled, “A Study on Ayurvedic Medicines in Medical Tourism with Special Reference to Kerala” discussed on Kerala’s medical tourism and the role of ayurveda in it. The study mainly identified the driving factors of medical tourism in Kerala and the major treatments that attract tourists. Study was utilized questionnaire and schedule method for collecting primary data and various journals and websites for secondary

data. From the analyses it has been identified a blend of tourism resources and health care resources in Kerala. Various rejuvenation and therapeutic treatments and facilities provided attract tourists. The study also made some criticisms against health tourism like illegal massage parlours and the practice of compelling health tourism providers to contribute a certain amount of their profit to public health care fund.

Sanjeev Rastogi et al., (2022) in the study “A Survey of Patients Visiting an Ayurvedic Teaching Hospital for Factors Influencing the Decision to Choose Ayurveda as a Health Care Provider”, identified the responsible factors influencing the decision to choose ayurveda. A survey of patients visiting an ayurvedic teaching hospital was done for the study. The data was collected using a questionnaire which was polished through a pilot study. The study primarily discussed these factors namely, pre-disposing factors, enabling factors and the need factors. The analysis was done for 21 sets of variables. The Z test was applied to check and confirm whether the observed opinions have any statistical significant difference while comparing it with the assumptions. According to the researcher’s point of view, the factors like relative safety, disease eradicating potential, belief etc, were the primary reasons for choosing ayurveda. The factors like affordability, accessibility and availability have least importance in deciding Ayurveda as a health care system.

Objectives

- To study the role of Ayurveda in Kerala’s health tourism.
- To analyse the treatment facilities and employment opportunities of Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier’s Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal in ayurvedic health tourism.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data was collected from the officials of the Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier’s Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal, through personal interviews. The secondary data was collected from various books, journals, official websites, etc.

Ayurveda Health Tourism in Kerala

Ayurveda is a century-old concept, meaning wisdom for longevity. It is one of India’s monumental contributions to the world. In India, this knowledge of Ayurveda originated to about 5000 years ago and is popularly called the “Mother of healing”. Essential information about this particular system of medicine has been recorded in Vedic texts, especially in Atharva Veda. The

Kerala tradition of Ayurveda is best known for its unique pharmacy and therapy characteristics. As rightly told in Ayurveda, “Arogyam Mulamuttamam”, it has given much more importance to “Arogya” (health). It is a system of medicine dealing with both rejuvenating the body, fighting stress, and also offers effective cure for several diseases including lifestyle diseases and also the chronic ones. At the beginning of the 20th century, after gaining democracy, India began seeking to revive ayurvedic traditions. Ayurveda was accepted as a medicine during this period, and the government supported its development. Legislation and policies for the assessment of Ayurvedic practice and education were developed. And regulations were made under the law on the production and distribution of ayurvedic medicines. Ayurveda's core concept is that the mind and body are interconnected, and the mind has the ability to heal and change the whole nature of a human.

Ayurveda and Kerala are synonymous with each other. Through Ayurveda, Kerala gains its popularity at the international level for its medical treatments. Its affordability, low costs, efficient medical service, etc. made the state a favorable destination for medical tourists all around the world. Since Ayurveda helps to rejuvenate both the mind and body with no side effects, it attracts not only the health tourists but also others from various parts around the world. Ayurveda is a major money earner for Kerala tourism, as it was a gateway to a large rise in the number of tourists to the state. Kerala is an ideal place for medical tourism. Globalization has given a push to the medical sector in the state. Today ayurvedic tourism of the state gained much popularity. There are numerous resorts, spa centers, and hospitals that in Kerala which offer hundreds of treatments to their customers. Airport pickup, accommodation, food, transportation and so many facilities were offered, besides medical treatment in the centers.

In the last three decades, the demand for ayurvedic treatments and medicines has been growing tremendously, both domestically and internationally. Its annual growth and contribution to the manufacturing sector in Kerala also register an upward trend. Driving by demand both from within and outside the country for ayurvedic products and treatments, there was modernization and innovation in this sector.

Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier’s Arya Vaidya Sala, Kottakkal

Arya Vaidya Sala (AVS), Kottakkal is a more than 117 years old charitable institution engaged in the practice and propagation of Ayurveda, situating in the Malappuram district of Kerala. AVS was established at Kottakkal in 1902 by the well-known physician Vaidyaratnam P S Varier (1869-1944). With the gurukula training in the science and practice of Ayurveda and

with further practical training in modern medicines and also with a clear cut motivation, he established this institution which marked a momentous change in the history of the development of Ayurveda in Kerala. Kottakkal Arya Vaidya Sala, a leader in the field of manufacturing and distributing ayurvedic medicines is the result of the devotion of three people - P.S Varier, who founded it; his nephew P Madhava Varier, who took over after his death; and Madhava Varier's younger brother P Krishna Varier, who made this one as a world's renowned institution and continues to lead it today. "The primary reason for the establishment of Arya Vaidya Sala is the conviction that our greatest duty is to make an effort to seek prestige in the future rather than waste time regretting the past".¹ -P.S. Varier, 1902.

Recognized as a pioneer in the field of Ayurveda, AVS is now a multi-unit, multi-functional and multidisciplinary organization significantly in clinical service, medicine manufacturing, distribution, research, education, herb cultivation, and academic documentation. There are four hospitals being operated by AVS, out of it, two were in Kottakkal itself, and one each in Delhi and Kochi, where the classical Panchakarma therapies and other special therapies are provided. There are three manufacturing units at Kottakkal, Kanjikode, and Nanjangud. These products are available to patients across the country through 26 branches and more than 1800 authorized dealers. Patients from both inside and outside the country visit here for various needs. Amongst these, there are peoples for curing chronic diseases as well as for rejuvenating treatments like Sukhachikitsa. Monsoon season is more suitable for these rejuvenating treatments. And the number of people preferring this type of treatment is increasing nowadays. The major treatments providing by this institution are,

- Pizhichil
- Navarakizhi
- Sirovasti
- Dhara
- Vasti
- Snehapanam
- Nasyam
- Podikkizhi
- Tarpanam
- Pachakizhi etc.

Besides these recently, there are treatments available for cancer, HIV Positive, and cardiac diseases. Three seasons are usually known to be best suitable for the service. They range from

¹ Quoted in Dr. P K Varier, October 2005, Smrithiparvam, Kottakkal Arya Vaidya Sala

mid-July to mid-August, from mid-October to mid-November, from mid-February to mid-March.

This centre offers wide range of facilities. The accommodation details are as follows:

**Table 1: Accommodation Details –
A Comparison between years 2019 and 2024**

Sl. No.	Type of Room	Facilities	Room Rent (Per Day) Rs. in 2019	Facilities	Room Rent (Per Day) Rs. in 2024
1	Super Deluxe Family Suite	Amply furnished A/c living room & bedroom (two beds), attached bathroom, treatment room, Kitchen, dining room, Refrigerator, TV, WiFi provided	6,500	Amply furnished A/c living room & bedroom (two beds), attached bathroom, treatment room, Kitchen, dining room, Refrigerator, TV, Kettle , WiFi provided	8,000 + 5% GST
2	Majestic A/c Rooms	Centrally A/c, Spacious room, separate bed section (two beds), drawing-dining section, attached bathroom, well furnished with two TVs, Refrigerator, WiFi	5,200	Centrally A/c, Spacious room, separate bed section (two beds), drawing-dining section, attached bathroom, well furnished with two TVs, Refrigerator, Kettle & WiFi	6,000 + 5% GST
3	Adisankara Suite (Two Types)	A/c bedroom (two beds), non-a/c living – cum – dining section. Attached treatment room, kitchen, bathroom, refrigerator, TV, WiFi provided	4,200/3,800	A/c bedroom (two beds), non-a/c living – cum – dining section. Attached treatment room, kitchen, bathroom, refrigerator, TV, Kettle , WiFi provided	5,000/4,500
4	Standard A/c Room (Two Types)	Normal A/c room with two beds, attached bathroom, balcony, TV, Refrigerator, WiFi provided. With/without attached kitchen and treatment room	2,350/1,850	Normal A/c room with two beds, attached bathroom, balcony, TV, Refrigerator, Kettle , WiFi provided. With/without attached kitchen and treatment room	2,900/2,300

5	Non-a/c Room (Two Types)	Non-A/c room (two beds), attached bathroom, TV, balcony With/without attached treatment room	1,550/1,150	Non-A/c room (two beds), attached bathroom, TV, Fridge, Kettle , balcony With/without attached treatment room	2,000/1,600
6	General Ward	12 bedded general wards (each bed is in a small cabin) Bathroom not attached. No advance reservation	300	12 bedded general wards (each bed is in a small cabin) Bathroom not attached. No advance reservation	450

Source: Official Records

Figure 1: A Comparison of Room Rents between the Years 2019 and 2024

Source: Official Records

There are A/C suite rooms and non-A/C rooms. The types of the room can be classified into six like, super deluxe family suite, majestic A/c rooms, Adisankara suite, standard A/c rooms, non-A/c rooms and general wards. Besides these, there is one charitable hospital where the accommodation and medication are completely free. All rooms except the general ward are amply furnished with modern amenities. Each room is for a patient only and the second bed in

the space is for the attendant. The attendant can often take advantage of care according to the recommendation of the doctor. There are some systematic and simple procedures for room booking. Both online and offline facilities are available. The initial stage is to contact one of the doctors in the department/branch of patients or via e-mail. When the doctors recommend for admitted care, it is needed to book a bed.

Table 2: Treatment and Medicine Cost (Expense Per Day)

Sl. No.	Type of Room	Expense Per Day (2019)		Expense Per Day (2024)	
		Treatment (Rs.)	Medicine (Rs.)	Treatment (Rs.)	Medicine (Rs.)
1	Super Deluxe Family Suite	2,600	900	3,400	1,000
2	Majestic A/c Rooms	2,600	900	3,400	1,000
3	Adisankara Suite (Two Types)	2,600	900	3,400	1,000
4	Standard A/c Room (Two Types)	2,600	900	3,400	1,000
5	Non-a/c Room (Two Types)	2,600	900	3,400	1,000
6	General Ward	2,600	900	3,400	1,000

Source: Official Records

Table-2 depicts the expense for treatment and medicine per day for the years 2019 and 2024. It was understood that the expenses for all categories of rooms for treatments was increased from Rs.2,600 to Rs.3,400 and for the medicines from Rs.900 to Rs.1,000. Thus it seems an increase in the expenses over the years.

The expenditures for various packages of treatments were mentioned in the following table and graph.

**Table 3: Expenditure (in Rupees) –
A Comparison between 2019 and 2024**

Sl. No.	Type of Room	Expenditure (in Rs.) – 2019			Expenditure (in Rs.) – 2024		
		14 Days	21 Days	28 Days	14 Days	21 Days	28 Days
1	Super Deluxe Family Suite	1,50,000	2,20,000	2,90,000	1,82,000	2,73,000	3,65,000
2	Majestic A/c Rooms	1,35,000	1,95,000	2,57,000	1,52,000	2,30,000	3,10,000
3	Adisankara Suite (Two Types)	1,18,000	1,75,000	2,35,000	1,33,000	2,00,000	2,80,000

4	Standard A/c Room (Two Types)	86,000	1,30,000	1,72,000	1,04,000	1,56,000	2,08,000
5	Non-a/c Room (Two Types)	75,000	1,12,000	1,48,000	90,000	1,35,000	1,80,000
6	General Ward	54,000	80,000	1,05,000	68,000	1,02,000	1,36,000

Source: Official Records

Figure 2: Expenditure of 14 Days Package (in Rupees) – A Comparison between 2019 and 2024

Source: Official Records

Figure-2 shows the expenditure of 14 days package in the years 2019 and 2024. Super deluxe family suite’s expenditure has risen from Rs.1,50,000 to Rs.1,82,000 (Rs.32,000 differences). Expenditures for majestic A/c rooms reached Rs.1,52,000 from Rs.1,35,000, Adisankara suite also increased room Rs.1,18,000 to Rs.1,33,000. Standard A/c rooms’ expenditure increased by Rs.18,000 and for Non-A/c the amount increased by Rs.23,000. The expenditure for general ward has also been rise from Rs.80,000 to Rs.1,02,000.

Figure 3: Expenditure of 21 Days Package (in Rupees) – A Comparison between 2019 and 2024

Source: Official Records

Figure-3 shows the expenditure of 21 days package in the years 2019 and 2024. Super deluxe family suite's expenditure has risen from Rs.2,20,000 to Rs.2,73,000 (Rs.32,000 differences). Expenditures for majestic A/c rooms reached Rs.2,30,000 from Rs.1,95,000, Adisankara suite also increased room cost Rs.1,75,000 to Rs.2,00,000. Standard A/c rooms' expenditure increased by Rs.26,000 and for Non-A/c the amount increased by Rs.15,000. The expenditure for general ward has also been rose from Rs.54,000 to Rs.68,000.

Figure 4: Expenditure of 28 Days Package (in Rupees) – A Comparison between 2019 and 2024

Source: Official Records

The above figure shows the expenditure of 28 days package, comparing the years between 2019 and 2024. The highest expenditure category in both these years were the super deluxe family suite, which was Rs.2,90,000 in 2019 and Rs.3,65,000 in 2024. The second top most was Majestic A/c rooms, which was rises from Rs.2,57,000 to Rs.3,10,000 in 2024. Adisankara suite also increased room expenditure Rs.2,35,000 to Rs.2,80,000. Standard A/c rooms' expenditure increased by Rs.36,000 and for Non-A/c the amount increased by Rs.32,000. The expenditure for general ward has also been increased from Rs.1,05,000 to Rs.1,36,000.

Table 4: Health Tourists Visits to Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal

Years	No. of Indians	No. of Foreigners
2013-2014	17,468	3,587
2014-2015	17,982	3,972
2015-2016	18,564	4,118
2016-2017	19,608	4,392
2017-2018	20,624	5,749
2018-2019	20,485	5,143
2019-2020	21,958	5,517
2020-2021	10,705	1,561
2021-2022	14,133	1,849
2022-2023	20,206	4,864

Source: Official Records

Figure 5: Health Tourists Visits to Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal

Source: Official Records

The above given data (Table-4 and Figure-5) shows the number of health tourists visits to Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal during the years 2013-2014 to 2022-2023. The data depicts an increasing trend over the years and a sudden fall in the year 2020-2021 due to the outbreak of the Covid-19. Later on also the number of tourists seems in a rising trend. But the overall trend shows a growth in the number of tourists to the centre, both foreigners and domestic tourists. The tourists within India have been reached to 20,206 in 2022-2023 which was 17,468 in 2013-2014. The foreign tourists were also reached to a better position while comparing it with the year 2013-2014. It was 3,587 in 2013-2014, which was later grown to 4,864 in 2022-2023. Thus it has been saying that the number of tourists are growing year by year, except during the Covid-19 periods.

Table 5: Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal**Head Office: Employment Position**

Category	Number of Employees
Administration level	125
Physicians	30
Treatment Assistants	294
Nurses	6
Nursing Assistants	20
Executives	5
Factory Workers	600
Raw Materials Collector	100
Attenders	50
Courier Section	5
Total	1,235

Source: Official Records

Figure 6: Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal**Head Office: Employment Position**

Source: Official Records

The above depicts data in table-5 and figure-6 show the employment position in the head office of the Vaidyaratnam P.S. Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal. The total number of employees is 1,235 in the head office. Based on the data, highest number of employees are working in the factory section (600), following the treatment level (294), administrating level (125) and the raw material collector (100). Next sections in the list in the number of people working are the attenders (50), physicians (30) and nursing attenders (20). The categories having very least number of employees were the nurses (6) and executives and courier section (5 each). The data thus states that, the sector is having a greater contribution in terms of employment in an economy.

Conclusion

Health Tourism is the most fertile area where we could get high yield by applying suitable inputs and exploring it. People's wellness and beauty consciousness has created a way for Health Tourism to rise in value. It is a thrust field. We are blessed with immense number of plants and other species. Unfortunately, we are not using it in its fullest form. It is easy to exploit these resources as soon. But by exploring these resources by using both traditional and modern methods would give us a fruitful result. As we have a strong heritage, enough resources and talented physicians and other improved infrastructure facilities, we could develop this and bring it to greater heights. The present study mainly examines the role of ayurveda in health tourism, its possibilities and opportunities in Kerala, and also analyses the treatment opportunities and employment position in the Vaidyaratnam P.S Varier's Ayurveda Sala, Kottakkal. Thus the overall analysis shows that Kerala can develop its image as the destination for Ayurvedic Health Tourism. Undoubtedly, the government plays a significant part in this. As a result, there is a greater reach while encouraging business owners to pursue the growth of ayurvedic-centred health tourism. Therefore, chances in Kerala would be more advantageous in drawing tourists and thereby growing the economy if a comprehensive strategy focused on the quality of services existed in effect.

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